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Editor's note

Throughout history as humanity, communication has been a key element in the development of societies. Even, and almost without fear of making some mistake, it could be said that communication is a *condition sine qua non* for the *Homo sapiens'* existence. The way in which we transmit our perceptions of reality and the exchange of ideas allows us to connect with other people to meet and recognize multiple forms of knowledge and wisdom that are key in the way we interact and participate in decision-making. The use and adoption of tools to improve communication and involvement between different actors have allowed the integration of multiple voices, the diversification of approaches to address socioenvironmental problems, and even the creation of policies and regulations that seek the common good.

In this issue, you will find an article in which we invite you to reflect on how communication and outreach can be decisive in the development and scope of different projects. This publication also contains a text written by the anthropologist Rubén Araujo on the characteristics and challenges associated with a couple of CCUS pilot projects in Mexico that would be implemented in territories with an indigenous population. In the *CO₂NVERSING* section, you will find an interview with Raúl Cedeño, editorial director of the *Petróleo&Energía* magazine, with whom we talked about corporate communication. In the *Yes, yes it is* section, we share with you some tools for the participation and involvement of the main stakeholders at different stages of the projects. Finally, in the *Take-Away* section, we list some suggestions and recommendations to explore and learn about other opinions, voices and realities aimed at the search for a common good. We hope you enjoy this issue and, if you wish, share your ideas and opinions with us.

The mysterious machine

By Jazmín Mota

There was an occasion when people from all over the world gathered for the reveal of a mysterious machine. Heads of state, experts from many disciplines, business people, but above all, people from society – of all ages, genders, regions, and beliefs – came together as this machine aroused great curiosity. At its revelation, people were shocked. It seemed so modern and new that it looked very special in the eyes of the spectators. People began to wonder about the purpose of the machine; Some wondered where they would place it and even imagined what it would be like if, by chance, they decided to install it near their homes or communities. Another group of people claimed that the machine could help their industries and businesses, or even work as a tourist attraction that would give them fame and recognition, because, in how many places in the world would it be possible to have a mysterious machine like that? Some thought that it had been designed to solve the great problems that afflicted them in those days; perhaps it was not only a mysterious machine but also magical. Others believed that it was just a distraction from the truly important things, that it was of little use and that having attended that meeting was a waste of time. Many ideas were exchanged about it, which varied from one person to another. The point was that not even those who had created it knew for sure what the machine could do...

Communication and involvement with society and the main stakeholders are key for developing any project or initiative, whether on a local or global scale. There are various ways of communicating and expressing our ideas, which are a shared representation of physical and social phenomena and the assumptions and perceptions we have of the world. Although "each head is a world" is a well-known quote, I would rather say that each head is a multiverse in a constant transformation that connects with others with similar dynamics. Our thoughts and way of perceiving the world are not static and depend on multiple factors. Every day new ideas are born and create stories that, when integrated, build narratives that express shared meanings. In this way, we express and exchange our perceptions about our environments and realities.

Exploring what people think, live and feel is a determining element for communication. Many very diverse realities can hardly be understood, recognized and shared without good communication. We often take for granted that other people share our way of seeing and perceiving the world, but this is not necessarily the case. For example, when we listen to a song—regardless of the genre—it may be our favorite song, and we want to listen to it again and again, but for someone else, it may not be so exceptional or even dislike it. In both cases, it can happen that months or years later, the perception of the same song has a very different or opposite effect. So, what does it depend on whether we like it or not at a particular moment? (Here, I'll let you make a mental list of all the answers that could come to mind) Whatever the reasons, they are all valid; but then if instead of a song, it was about the implementation or development of a project or policy, how do we agree?

Integrating knowledge and opinions allows us to listen, recognize and create proposals better adapted to the realities and contexts the projects or policies seek to serve. Today, many technologies that offer alternatives to major socio-environmental problems involve significant risks and investments. In many cases, the possible positive or negative impacts its implementation may have in the medium and long term are unknown. Therefore, understanding and uncovering existing narratives of the problems we want to solve can be useful for selecting the technologies, defining their objectives and how they would work. We must avoid creating lock-in mechanisms that tie us for years to projects that, over time, are incompatible with the socioenvironmental dynamics. We need more plural and critical narratives based on the connection between all the social, environmental, political and technological elements to avoid expectations that are either too optimistic or too pessimistic. The idea is to co-design more comprehensive proposals that address real problems.

Success or failure of projects, from small-scale eco-technologies (such as sustainable wood stoves) to large-scale mega-infrastructure (such as CO₂-based fuels), depends on communication and stakeholders' involvement from the stage of defining the problem, monitoring and implementation. Nowadays, It is difficult to find cases in which stakeholders participate actively in decision-making. On the contrary, ignoring the realities and needs of those who should be benefited from the projects is a common reason for socioenvironmental conflicts. Frequently a group of people decide in an isolated and unilateral way what others need. The motivations for implementing these technologies often respond solely to the interests of the industry, government or business, leaving aside other interested parties.

Currently, methodologies, regulations and mechanisms promote better communication and involvement with society. Unfortunately, there is still a long way to go to ensure that these forms of participation and integration of people in these processes are effective, well-informed and used throughout the different stages of project development. To achieve this, wide adoption of transdisciplinary research is necessary to encourage people to be active collaborators in the approach to the problem, the identification and selection of solutions, and their follow-up. Participation is not just about "seating people around the table" but about giving them a place to achieve actual transformations as co-creators.

Remember the mystery machine? It would seem almost impossible to agree on what it was created for, right? What I would propose to find the answer is to think of a strategy in which 1) its creators explain how it was made in a language that is understandable to everyone and give access to information transparently, avoiding black box models; 2) defining the objectives and scope of the machine —knowing what we can and want to use it for is one of the most important steps—; 3) listen to the different voices and opinions of all those involved and create safe spaces for dialogue and exchange of ideas, all of them valid, and that deserves to be heard and shared; 4) use data and scientific and non-scientific knowledge to identify the possible impacts and scope of the use of the machine over time; and 5) establish follow-up, decision-making and monitoring mechanisms.

Beyond the physical and technological functions, the non-tangible relationships and interactions around the adoption of technologies must be considered if we seek to provide solutions to real and complex problems, such as socio-environmental ones. These strategies should lead us to learn, promote and incorporate better communication and involvement mechanisms, as well as the use and adoption of more comprehensive and participatory methodologies for decision-making, project design and implementation.

...the outcome of the story depends on who writes it, but also who reads it, and how all parties participate in making decisions and using 'this mysterious machine'.

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INDIGENOUS POPULATION AND CARBON CAPTURE AND STORAGE PROJECTS IN MEXICO

By Rubén Araujo

It is more and more frequent that implementing projects in any economic sector in Mexico leads to knowing at least something about the people living in the area where the projects will be developed. The energy sector is the only one with regulations in terms of social impact. Project promoters must evaluate possible effects on the territory, the communities and people's livelihoods. This tendency to get to know and dialogue with the stakeholders of the projects to harmonize them socially and communally has not been enough. Even so, there are good experiences in the interaction between the actors, their particular visions of development and their similarities or discrepancies in interests and aspirations.

Two experiences of this type occurred a few years ago for preparing the carbon capture, utilization and storage (CCUS) pilot projects in Mexico, whose objective was to test this technology and subsequently scale it up to a commercial level. These two projects would be developed in the state of Veracruz, and for both, it was required to apply the respective safeguard regarding indigenous peoples. There was reasonable doubt about the presence or absence of an indigenous population in the areas of influence since the available demographic data from the Population and Housing Census recorded a small number of people identified as indigenous. Consequently, an investigation was conducted to determine the presence of an indigenous population in the two areas of influence of the project to determine the ethnic status of the people and the anthropological criteria that define an indigenous community.

The demographic approach to estimate the indigenous population in Mexico

Since the 1990s, the National Indigenous Institute – today the National Institute of Indigenous Peoples (INPI) – has coordinated, together with INEGI, a method to estimate the indigenous population in Mexico. The methodology is based on identifying the indigenous household and quantifying the population from the total of its members. In addition, it is considered that a home is a space for the identification and transmission of culture within which ties of kinship and affectivity affect the development and transmission of identities. In the home, decisions and resources are shared, and community networks of life and territorial relations are built, mediated by a collective vision. Their role in individuals' socialisation and cultural transmission allows us to assume that there are shared codes and identities in households where one or more people are indigenous [1].

In this sense, the indigenous household is made up of the total population, even if they do not speak an indigenous language, but who live in households whose head of a family, spouse and/or ascendant has declared that they speak an indigenous language. Additionally, the population that speaks an indigenous language, but lives in non-indigenous households, is also considered.

The cultural approach to conceptualize the indigenous community

The Political Constitution of Mexico conceives indigenous peoples *as those who descend from populations that inhabited the current territory of the country at the beginning of colonization and who retain their own social, economic, cultural and political institutions, or part of them*, by the definition of Convention 169 of the International Labor Organization. It is agreed that the awareness of their indigenous identity is the fundamental criterion to determine to whom its legal provisions will apply and that it supports the “self-ascription” criterion used in demographic methods for identifying the indigenous population.

Another matter is moving from the legal definition of indigenous people and individuals to that of an indigenous community. We resort to other elements of anthropological analysis. The most used is the linguistic criterion, especially for statistical and census surveys. Still, it is insufficient because there are segments of the population that, although they do not speak an indigenous language, share expressions that suggest a way of thinking and acting as if they were. On the contrary, some people do not identify themselves as such, although they speak an indigenous language. Hence, we have to resort to a broader approach based on the concept of culture.

Although there is no agreed or generally applicable definition for all those elements that characterize the indigenous, the ethnic and the culture, one of the most common definitions is that of Guillermo Bonfil Batalla, which indicates that *“an ethnic group has an autonomous cultural environment, from which it defines its collective identity (ethnic identity) and makes possible the reproduction of its limits as a differentiated society”* [2]. In other words, a form of autonomous culture can be the awareness of their identity expressed in the self-affirmation of having an indigenous language. Other elements specific to people’s identity are involved, allowing them to be differentiated from other indigenous societies or broader societies. In this sense, the dimension and limits of an indigenous group concerning others, indigenous or not, are defined by the use it makes of its own identity since, in this way, the group is defined and assumed as a political entity that has the exclusive right to control a universe of its own cultural elements [3].

In this way, we can better understand the classic definition that an indigenous community is conceived as a unit of population, territory and language but that is complemented by the self-awareness of the affirmation of identity, that is, of culture expressed in collective practices of language, economics, medicine, religion, among others.

The indigenous community, then, is not only a representation of the collectivity where elements of a group's identity are expressed but of the conscious decision of what the group wants to express as its own.

Presence of indigenous population associated with CCUS pilot projects in Mexico

In Mexico, two CCUS pilot projects were planned. The first was a pilot CO₂ capture project, which would be located in the *ejido*¹ San Miguel Mecatepec, Veracruz. According to the INEGI, the population of San Miguel in 2010 was 2,197 people, of which only 44 declared that they spoke an indigenous language, and 150 lived in an indigenous home.

To identify the indigenous population, a series of interviews were conducted with community representatives (such as the municipal agent and inhabitants close to the Project area) to identify indigenous people through elements of the Totonaca culture, which is the closest indigenous region. It confirmed the presence of an indigenous population, not from this ethnic group, but from the Otomi from the Huasteca indigenous region. Several of the heads of families who were interviewed still spoke an indigenous language and little Spanish, and others only understood the Otomi language but no longer spoke it. Each of these families arrived approximately 20 years ago without knowing each other; later, they were related by marriage alliance of some of its members. Now, they make up a group of approximately 50 people. About half continue to speak the Otomi language, and all members share the same cultural references of common origin.

¹ In Mexico, the *ejido* constitutes one of the modalities of social property (the other modality is communal land). In terms of area, social property constitutes 52% of the national territory.

Despite the indigenous group not representing the majority of the population, it stands out for the public manifestation of its cultural expressions associated with pagan and religious traditions, such as the celebration of carnival and Eastern, which they even share with other Otomi groups in nearby *ejidos*. Although there is not an indigenous community in its entirety, there is a colony of migrants where the Otomi group is in the process of community reconstitution with cultural attachment to their community of origin, to which many of them cannot return for the same security reasons that forced them out. Today, culture brings them together again, and they reproduce their festivals and religious beliefs that give them identity. In the linguistic context, another transformation process can be seen: grandparents speak Otomí better than Spanish, parents speak Spanish better than Otomi, and few children speak the indigenous language.

The second pilot project, focused on the use of CO₂ and geological storage, is located in the Guillermo Prieto *ejido* belonging to the municipality of Coatzacoalcos, Veracruz. In this case, the municipal agent did not identify any person who spoke an indigenous language or could imply belonging to this sector due to any specific characteristic or cultural manifestation.

According to data from the 2010 Population and Housing Census, Guillermo Prieto registered 6 speakers of the indigenous language and 29 people from households whose head of family spoke the indigenous language. In the case of other nearby *ejidos*, although they have ancestors who speak an indigenous language, they do not recognize themselves as indigenous because they do not speak the language, in addition to the fact that they do not exercise any collective practice of identity.

A fundamental step to knowing the possible impacts that CCUS projects may have in Mexico is the recognition and identification of indigenous peoples living in these projects' areas of influence. In regions like Mexico, where there is great cultural and ethnic diversity, a detailed analysis is required to guarantee that the projects not only provide benefits in terms of emission reduction but also guarantee the protection of the communities, identities, culture and environment where they are implemented. The pilot projects have not been carried out, but the data and experience obtained for their design and preparation are an essential source of information and knowledge for adopting just, more equal and respectful practices for people and the environment.

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CONVERSANDO

CONVERSING

Corporate communication: sharing and opening up knowledge in *Petróleo&Energía*

Interview with **Raúl Cedeño**, by **Paola Massyel García Meneses** and **Isaac Galicia Pineda**.

Raúl Cedeño has a degree in Communication Sciences from La Salle University. He has worked in corporate communication in companies in the cultural, financial, raw material and energy sectors, including DuPont, the accounting firm Mazars and the publishing house Santillana. He is currently the Editorial Director of the leading magazine in the energy sector in Mexico: *Petróleo&Energía*. His journalistic work includes interviews with prominent authors and current managers and figures from the public and private sectors.

Humans are curious and observant by nature. These characteristics have led us to understand and seek explanations of our surroundings. The accumulated information generated by finding answers has led us to what we now call knowledge. Although knowledge is universal, and we should all have access to it, some people have a closer approach to the information and knowledge generated daily. Free access to information is a right of humanity. The right to science is explicit in article 27 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights: *“everyone has the right to freely take part in the community’s cultural life, to enjoy the arts and to participate in any scientific progress and the benefits that result from it”*. If, as stakeholders, we generate relevant information, it is also our responsibility to transmit it. This transmission is a great challenge, and there are several ways to do it, such as scientific communication, which has been defined as a simple way to transmit concepts based on reliable information. Magazines, gazettes, and newspapers are ways of disseminating information. Some people have dedicated their careers to strategically delivering relevant data and knowledge related to global and energy change issues. We talked with an expert in corporate communication who leads one of the most prestigious magazines in the energy sector: *Petróleo&Energía*.

Q: From the experiences in your professional career, **what would be the strategies you have used to permeate concepts related to carbon capture or issues related to carbon?**

A: First of all, our concept was very limited to the oil industry; in other words, we were only focused on that segment. In fact, the magazine was born as a publication dedicated to the oil industry in Mexico. Still, in these 20 years of experience, we have evolved and addressed issues deeply related to the industry. Some of them are carbon sequestration, sustainability, and the sector’s implications. We have learned that these issues have become very relevant in the last two years.

The new ways of seeing the industry, based on ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) compliance, are the new parameters of companies, for which there are mechanisms such as carbon credits or the commitments of companies to achieve net-zero¹. In our experience, we have had to find a way to bring these trends to our audience to understand that today 1) it is not just a new topic, but something that we must attend to; 2) it is an issue of compliance by companies; and 3) it includes monetary issues since non-compliance with certain guidelines implies economic sanctions, therefore it is forced and necessary, and of which we are just learning.

¹ Net-zero emissions refer to achieving a global balance between greenhouse gas emissions produced and greenhouse gas emissions removed from the atmosphere. <https://www.climatecouncil.org.au/resources/what-does-net-zero-emissions-mean/>

Q: Have you found links between the energy sector and sustainability?

A: Yes, definitely. Today one of the biggest trends is the digitalization of manufacturing, focused on productivity and the search for efficiency in the use of energy, which results in cost savings and emissions. Although the link between these two sectors is sometimes not very clear, I think we are making an effort, at least from my experience.

Q: What strategies would allow reaching a larger audience that includes other sectors such as academia, local governments, the general population and industry?

A: That's a great question. Fortunately, we have an excellent response because the model we have allows us to be a means of communication that can become massive. Nowadays, there is an overload of information and the new forms of communication demand that its transmission must be much more efficient and accurate. In *Petróleo&Energía* we have found a way through public relations and alliances with different sectors of the population and industry. We focus on those who need to be reached with this information to **achieve profound changes**. In our experience, we see that today there is a powerful trend in the country. At the local government level, more and more energy agencies are changing to meet the regulations; this includes parameters related to sustainability and emissions control so that they can bring and generate energy to their states and achieving not only the energy demand but also the international standards aligned with the 2030 Agenda, the Paris Agreement and ESG compliance to apply for carbon credits.

I think that one of the main strategies is to approach the local level. The media has focused on Mexico City many times. Approaching the local level entails the **creation of alliances and strategies** so that the information can travel to other audiences. We have sought to reach some groups and sectors directly through forums, webinars and presentations to publicize what we are doing. We have successful cases in Monterrey, Nuevo León, and very recently in Córdoba, Veracruz, where we have taken this information and found that the general population is also interested, as well as the local government and academia. **An ecosystem is being built where we can spread knowledge**. We are interested in implementing strategies that help us continue our communication work, not necessarily with the physical product (the magazine) but through other actions.

Q: Considering this ecosystem under construction and your experience, have you found a benefit in face-to-face activities versus social networks like Facebook and Twitter, which focus on gaining millions of likes to get closer to local communities and groups?

A: I believe everything involved in the media must be divided into two strategies. Although the information exists and is free, businesses focused on communication have to feed a payroll and an operation and require advertising strategies. This advertising, as such, is sometimes not affordable for the public or companies within the republic, but it is a segment that has to be informed. So, in the end, the benefit is more significant because actions are taken so that the information reaches the local industry on time and is transmitted within the community. For us, the magazine continues to be a business for sharing knowledge across large conglomerates in the sector to small and medium-sized companies. In this way, we can transmit the message about the opportunities to migrate from past practices to new ones where better energy efficiency can be implemented and contribute to net zero and decarbonization. These points are not of economic value to the magazine, but they become a topic of interest for it.

Q: For you, Raúl, what is sustainability within the sector in which you work?

A: For me, it is a responsibility to use resources for our benefit without harming third parties. **I believe that sustainability is sometimes misunderstood as a "green" or "clean" idea or something without a carbon footprint. It is also about acknowledging the effects and consequences of everything we do; no matter the magnitude, we consume resources.** Sustainability is a responsible consumption done in the cleanest and safest way.

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

Participatory Tools

Almost eight billion people live in the world. To address the increasingly larger and more complex challenges, it is necessary to work together to integrate people and organizations that, with their training, experience and different points of view, can develop and propose different perspectives, improve the understanding of the contexts and problems they share, and generate a collective commitment to achieve changes for the common good.

It is necessary to highlight the voice of the different actors using tools that vary according to the stage of the participatory practice and are focused on connection, shared language, divergence, co-creation, convergence and commitment. Here we share some of them:

CONNECTION

The objective of these tools is to encourage dialogue between participants in order to clarify what the problem is.

Appreciative narrative

It seeks to rediscover and reorganize the proposals of the participants, instead of trying to solve the problem.

Rules of the game

It helps to discuss the rules or principles of interaction to carry out activities or the participation between various actors.

SHARED LANGUAGE

These tools serve to conduct a deep analysis of the problem and open the conversation to the different perspectives of the group to build a base of shared knowledge.

World Cafe

It consists of a conversation where participants can discuss and share ideas in a warm and friendly environment.

Force field analysis

It analyzes the forces for and against the topic of interest through graphic elements.

DIVERGENCE

With these tools, differences in understanding, vision and assessment of the topic of interest are analyzed to develop commitments stronger and propose solutions.

Six thinking hats

It is a role-playing game that allows participants to consider a decision from various points of view.

Guided fantasy

It invites the participants to imagine situations related to the topic in question and then share and discuss them together.

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

CO-CREATION

These tools encourage participants to develop various options considering different perspectives and voices.

Open space

It facilitates debate on a topic through group discussions.

Belbin Team Roles

It explores the roles of the participants in their work environments to optimize teamwork.

CONVERGENCE

They are tools to create as much shared knowledge as possible and generate a range of clear options for decision making.

Prioritize and rank

It allows selecting the most relevant ideas once several opinions have been generated, which are ranked by the vote of the participants.

Silence

It invites the participants to reflect silently on the topic of interest and then share their ideas.

COMMITMENT

The objective of these tools is to facilitate decision-making and agreements.

Fishbowl

It incentivizes a discussion among some participants while others listen and can join in as well if they wish.

Option one and a half

It helps to use two solutions to develop a third that is intermediate between the two initial points of view.

If you want to know more about these and other participatory tools, we invite you to consult the links in the references.

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- <https://www.worldometers.info/es/poblacion-mundial/>
- <https://designthinking.gal/tecnicas-de-creatividad-los-seis-sombros-para-pensar/>
- <https://www.belbin.es/test-belbin-informes/>

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

Unscramble the secret message by arranging the letters to form the words related to the participatory tools. Then complete the sentence using the letters in the numbered boxes.

MCMOIMTTEN	12	1				3	6		7	4		
MCMOIMTTEN							2	5				
GNIEEDVECR												
TAIO -NOECCR								9				
ONONEITCNC												
DASREH	10	8										
AENLAUGG	11											

W	1	2		K	3	4	5		6	1	5	7	6	8	7	2		
5	7	4	7	2	9	6	7	10	2	7	9	11	12	8	9	4	5	7

Answers: COMMITMENT, CONVERGENCE, DIVERGENCE, CO-CREATION, CONNECTION, SHARED LANGUAGE
 WORKING TOGETHER GENERATES REAL CHANGE

PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

Our list of recommendations for this issue includes materials ranging from readings, documentaries, and podcasts to events and seminars with which you can learn more about transdisciplinary and the importance of communication and outreach.

Book: Transdisciplinarity Manifesto

Today's problems are complex in nature and require new strategies to be understood and addressed in practice. Transdisciplinary expands our way of approaching reality and constitutes a fundamental concept that implies a reconstruction of our way of thinking and conceiving knowledge and the world. The book can be downloaded for free at the following link:

<https://edgarmorinmultiversidad.org/index.php/libros-sin-costo/85-la-transdiscipliniedad-manifiesto.html>

Material: The Multi-Stakeholder Partnership (MSP) Guide

This guide is a work of the Wageningen Center for Development Innovation (WC DI) and is a tool for designing and facilitating multi-stakeholder partnerships to address complex sustainability challenges. The guide and other tools are available in Spanish, English and French.

The MSP Guide – MSP Guide

Book: Dialogues on Transdiscipline

This book compiles the experiences, reflections, discussions and proposals of a group of researchers and academics on transdiscipline to build frontier knowledge. It is a work conceived with the interest of providing an enjoyable reading for reflections on the transgression of disciplinary boundaries. The book can be downloaded from the following link:

<https://portallibro.com/dialogos-sobre-transdisciplina/>

Podcast: The great socioenvironmental problems

This podcast from the University Coordination for Sustainability (COUS) presents the opinions of specialists on different topics about socio-environmental problems and emphasizes how environmental impacts are strongly associated with social problems.

<https://cous.sdi.unam.mx/cous/?seccion=podcast>

Documentary: The energy of the people and the Lights of the resistance campaign

In Mexico and Guatemala, energy production may, in some cases, involve privatization and the dispossession of natural assets to meet growing industrial energy demand. This documentary allows you to discover how rural and urban communities made a commitment to produce their own electricity and move towards fair, popular and sustainable energy models, which constitutes a challenge to the system and the consideration of energy as a common good and a right for everyone.

<https://www.laenergiadelospueblos.com/>

Project and documentary: Transgrass

Transgrass is a project that innovatively combined collaborative video, interactive technology, surveys and a series of workshops to develop a transdisciplinary platform for the integration of diverse forms of knowledge and for the co-generation of shared solutions for the management and changing conditions of communal pastures in the Scottish Highlands. A sample of the importance of transdisciplinary work for the solution of socio-environmental problems.

<https://www.hutton.ac.uk/research/projects/TRANSGRASS>

Movie: Don't look up

An American satire of "science fiction" where the gaps between science, government, industry and society are appreciated, and how disconnection and particular interests can represent a barrier to addressing global problems on which the survival of humanity and other forms of life depend. life on earth.

<https://www.netflix.com/title/81252357>

Documentary: Latin America: The false myth of clean energy

This documentary exposes how the "development" discourse has served to promote extractivist projects and megaprojects implemented without the consent of local communities. Under the pretext of climate change, capitalism presents ideas such as "clean energy" and "carbon neutral", whose initiatives exacerbate dispossession and, far from questioning the roots of global warming, seek to disguise the image of those responsible for the devastation.

<https://avispa.org/latinoamerica-el-falso-mito-de-las-energias-limpias/>

Webinar: Energy transition or regression?

It is organized by the University Seminar on Society, Environment and Institutions, SUSMAI. Coordinator: Dr Leticia Merino. Topic: Transition or energy regression? Participants: Gabriela Vázquez, Jorge Villareal, Marisol Anglés, Luca Ferrari, Gabriel Baeza. Moderator: Adrián Fernández. Production and streaming: Alfonso de la Vega. More information at www.susmai.unam.mx and www.observatorio.susmai.unam.mx

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FQu18TSzcz0>

Event: 3rd National Meeting of Ecotechnologies

From October 20 to 22, conferences, round tables, workshops and a fair will be held related to ecotechnologies applied to water, food, energy, housing and waste management in a post-pandemic recovery context. The event will take place at the UNAM facilities, Campus Morelia, Michoacán. For more information, see the following link:

<https://ecotec.unam.mx/eventos-talleres/3er-encuentro-nacional-de-ecotecnologias>

Magazine: Petróleo&Energía

With 17 years of history, the renowned magazine is an informative proposal for all sectors that converge within the international energy market. It was conceived and produced by the Mexican publishing group Ferráez Comunicación, the same publishing house as Líderes Mexicanos.

<https://petroleoenergia.com/>

Book: The seven knowledge necessary for the education of the future

Framed within the paradigms of complexity and transdisciplinarity, this work by renowned philosopher, sociologist and essayist Edgar Morin describes seven essential actions to reorient education towards sustainability. Morin points out that one of the most important challenges will be to modify our way of thinking and to educate ourselves to face the speed and unpredictability of the changes that characterize our complex reality.

<https://universoabierto.org/2021/07/15/los-siete-saberes-necesarios-para-la-educacion-del-futuro-3/>
<https://multiversidadreal.edu.mx/edgar-morin-o-el-elo-gio-del-pensamiento-complejo/>

Mexico City, México, 2022